

Coordination of cobalt(II), nickel(II) and copper(II) with Schiff base derived from 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde and 2-monopropanolamine

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Manuscript received 15 June 1999, accepted 3 September 1999

The complexes of Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} with Schiff base derived from 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde and 2-monopropanolamine have been prepared. The octahedral structure has been assigned to these compounds, excepting the Cu^{II} compound which has a distorted octahedral geometry.

Complexes with Schiff bases derived from 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde are used for extracting some metal ions. In most of these complexes¹, the ligand coordinates to the metal ions through both nitrogen and sulphur atoms.

We report here the synthesis of the Schiff base derived through the condensation of 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde (2-TFCA) and 2-monopropanolamine (2-MPA). This compound can be a bi- or polydentate ligand, because it contains three donor atoms: nitrogen, sulfur and oxygen. With this ligand, Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} (in the molar ratio 1 : 2) complexes have been prepared.

Results and Discussion

The Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} compounds with Schiff base derived from 2-thiophenecarboxaldehyde and 2-monopropanolamine are powder having high melting points (Table 1). They are not soluble in chloroform, ethanol and ethyl ether, with low solubility in methanol and acetone and more in DMF. Based on the elemental analysis the formulae [ML₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}) and [ML₂Cl₂] (M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}) have been suggested. The molar conductivity data indicate the

nonelectrolytic nature for all the complexes.

The intense IR ligand band at 1640 cm⁻¹ (C=N) occurs at lower frequencies in the metal complexes ($\Delta\nu = 20\text{--}50$ cm⁻¹). This suggests coordination of the azomethine group through the nitrogen atom. Also, the band ascribed to ν_{CSC} (900 cm⁻¹) in the free ligand spectrum is shifted to a lower region by about 30–45 cm⁻¹ in all the complexes, suggesting coordination through S atom of thiophene ring². The ligand band at 650 cm⁻¹, assigned to the asymmetric ν_{CS} , is shifted to lower frequency, and the symmetric ν_{CS} (from 685 cm⁻¹) completely disappears after complexation. This also confirms that the S atom participates in the coordination³

In the IR spectrum of the ligand, a band at 1120 cm⁻¹, characteristic of the vibration frequency of the C-OH_{sec} group can be observed. In the spectra of the [ML₂Cl₂] this band appears at 1129, 1115 and 1120 cm⁻¹, respectively, but in the case of [ML₂] this band disappears. On the basis of these data, it can be concluded that in [ML₂] the ligand coordinates through O atom⁴. The proof on N and O atoms coordination is demonstrated by the bands at 415–420 (which appear in all the complexes) and 448–450 cm⁻¹ (in [ML₂])⁵.

The information referring to the geometry of these compounds is obtained from the electronic spectra in solution and from values of the magnetic moments.

The UV spectrum of the ligand reveals two bands assigned to the transitions $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$. These transitions are also found in the spectra of the complexes but shifted to lower frequencies ($\Delta\nu = 1200\text{--}3000$ cm⁻¹), confirming the coordination of the ligand to the metal ions. [CoL₂] and [CoL₂Cl₂] show two new absorption bands at 20000 and 10500 cm⁻¹, and 21100 and 11000 cm⁻¹, respectively, ascribed to the transitions ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (F) and

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the complexes*

Compd	M p °C	Colour	μ_{eff} B M	Λ_{M} $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$
L	110	Mustard	–	–
C ₈ H ₁₁ ONS				
[CoL ₂]	250	Pink	4.83	5.00
[CoL ₂ Cl ₂]	215	Brown	5.04	9.20
[NiL ₂]	140	Green	3.12	3.55
[NiL ₂ Cl ₂]	160	Yellow	3.22	2.76
[CuL ₂ Cl ₂]	180	Green	1.93	5.92

*All complexes gave satisfactory metal, S, N and Cl analyses

${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)$. These transitions are characteristic of the compounds with an octahedral geometry of the Co^{II} ion⁶, a fact that is confirmed by the values of the effective magnetic moment (4.83, 5.04 B.M.).

The $[\text{NiL}_2]$ and $[\text{NiL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ spectra are specific to the Ni^{II} ion within octahedral environment⁷. The magnetic moment values (3.12 and 3.22 B.M.) observed for these compounds reveal the octahedral stereochemistry.

The electronic spectrum of $[\text{CuL}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ exhibits a band at 16300 cm^{-1} . This broad unsymmetric band may be due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in octahedral geometry. The magnetic moment value for this compound is about 1.9 B.M. These data suggest a distorted octahedral geometry⁸.

The structure of these complexes is suggested to be octahedral, excepting the Cu^{II} compound which has a distorted octahedral structure.

Experimental

$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{11}\text{ONS}$ ligand : The Schiff base was prepared by mixing ethanolic solution of 2-TFCA (0.001 mol, 25 ml) with ethanolic solution of 2-MPA (0.001 mol, 25 ml) and refluxing the mixture for 6 h on a water-bath. The solution was then concentrated until a dark-brown oily liquid was obtained. After evaporation of the excess of the solvent and friction with a glass wand, a mustard coloured solid was obtained. It was more soluble in acetone and ethyl ether and less soluble in CCl_4 .

$[\text{ML}_2]$ ($M = \text{Co}^{II}$ and Ni^{II}) : To an ethanolic solution of $\text{MCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}^{II}$ and Ni^{II}) (0.001 mol, 50 ml) an ethanolic solution of 2-TFCA/2-MPA (0.002 mol, 50 ml) was added with stirring. After 30 min, the resulting complexes were washed with ethanol and dried over P_2O_5 under reduced pressure.

$[\text{ML}_2\text{Cl}_2]$ ($M = \text{Co}^{II}$, Ni^{II} and Cu^{II}) : To a hot ethanolic solution of 2-TFCA/2-MPA (0.002 mol, 50 ml), a hot ethanolic solution of $\text{MCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($M = \text{Co}^{II}$ and Ni^{II}) and $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.001 mol, 50 ml) was added with stirring. After refluxing for 8 h on a water-bath, the solution was concentrated under reduced pressure and kept overnight at room temperature. The complexes were separated (except for the Cu^{II} complex combination which was prepared without refluxing). They were filtered, washed with ethanol and dried on P_2O_5 at low pressure.

The ligand and complexes were analysed for M, S and Cl by conventional methods⁹, while C, H and N by microanalytical methods. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a BIO-RAD FTS 135 spectrophotometer and UV-VIS spectra (DMF) on a UNICAM UV/VIS UV-4 spectrophotometer. Magnetic moment was determined by Faraday method. A K 612 conductivity meter was used.

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